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POGIL Effect On Acquisition Of Science Process Skills In Acid-Base Concepts Among Students Of Different Reasoning Abilities In Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja

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ABSTRACT

This research employed quasi experimental control group design using an accessible population of five thousand, five hundred and sixty-six (5,566) chemistry students. Two intact science classes of ninety one (91) students were sampled using simple and stratified random sampling. The research instruments were Acquisition of Science Skills in Acid-Base Concepts (ASSABC), and Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning (LCTSR). The statistical tools were Mean difference and ANCOVA. One of the research questions is “to what extent will the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL be different?” A major hypothesis among others is that the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL will not be significantly different. An important finding among others is that the extent to which the acquisition of science skills of transitional and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL is significantly different, hence one of the conclusions arrived at is that a strong correlation exist between reasoning ability and acquisition of science process skills after treatment. It was therefore recommended that research scientists in government research institutes should prepare science process skill acquisition packages for interactive session annually for science teachers and students’ training.

Keywords: Acid-base concepts, formal thought, POGIL, reasoning ability and science process skill.

INTRODUCTION

This study is an attempt to examine the possibility that teachers’ application of process-oriented guided-inquiry learning (POGIL) to teaching/learning processes might enhance the achievement of the desired learning outcomes which is better acquisition of science process skill. Mari (2016) points to teachers’ inability to use effective methods that could enhance meaningful learning of the concepts thought, leads to poor academic performance. Mari, Ali & Ibrahim (2024) identifies uninspiring methods of science teaching by science teachers as a link to poor academic performance in science and also a link to incapacitating science students from developing relevant skills necessary for creative thinking. De Gale & Boiselle (2015) establishes that learners demonstrated persistent difficulties inter-converting chemical knowledge through macroscopic, microscopic and symbolic form. The difficult chemistry concepts include Acid, Base and Salts among others seemingly difficult concepts.

Regarding the detection of the problem of poor academic performance as highlighted in Mari, Ali & Ibrahim (2024), scholars carried out a number of researches (Oloyede 2012; Barthlow, 2011; Ogunleye & Bamidele, 2013; Ayuba, 2014; De Gale & Boiselle 2015; Njokwu & Eze-odurukwe 2015; Meharunnisa & Hameed, 2016; Utley & Calik 2016; Keller, 2017 and Bala, 2018) indicating a

conclusion that chemistry students' poor academic performances created a sensitive problem related to poor operational thought and lack of skillfulness among chemistry students for all stakeholders in science education. The problem calls for a critical examination of how POGIL, a discovery learning instructional method rooted in problem solving phases, can improve and possibly bridge the gap in acquisition of science process skills between concrete through transition to formal reasoners among chemistry students. This research is concerned with determining the possibility of applying POGIL instructional strategy to resolve the following problems:

1. Teachers' inability to use effective methods that could enhance meaningful learning of the concepts they teach (Mari 2016);
2. Students' inability to link acid-base concepts with daily phenomena (as contexts) highlights the need for further research on acid-base chemistry (Utley & Calik (2016).
3. Scholarly works pointed to the reality of poor response to Piagetian type tasks for measuring formal operational thinking among senior secondary school students (poor thinking/science skills) (Demide, 2000; Oloyede, 2012).

In numerous studies, scholars like De Gale (2015) who examine effect of POGIL on academic performance and academic confidence; and the work of Inaroh et.al (2016) which examined effect of POGIL strategy based on Intertextual Learning of acid-base concepts yet the gap of absence of study on effect of POGIL on formal thought dichotomy and science process skill acquisition necessitates this research.

LITERATURE/ THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

One of the primary reasons for undertaking research in education, particularly in science education is to determine the most effective instructional strategy which can enhance learning (of scientific concepts and science process skills acquisition). Where academic performances are poor, suitable instructional strategies are adopted and as Mari (2016) observes, the use of effective strategies can improve learners' academic performances. If academic performances are already good, suitable instructional strategies provide opportunities for interaction that allows problem solving, creativity and acquisition of skills; these in turn builds learners and lifts their academic performances to greater heights or make them more proficient in use of science process skills to solve science related problems. National Research Council (NRC, 2016), recommends that state and local leaders in science education should provide teachers with models of classroom instruction that provide opportunities for interaction in the classroom where students carry out investigations, talk and write about their observations of phenomena, leading to their emerging understanding of scientific ideas and ways to test them. The implementation of this can enhance science students' acquisition of science process skills.

Science process skills are problem solving skills used by scientists in doing science and can be acquired by students of whatever level of education. As Michael (1990) defines science process skills, these skills are a set of broadly transferable abilities appropriate to many science disciplines and reflective of the behavior of scientists. Mathew, (2012) opines that science process skills are commonly described as the building block of inquiry and investigation. As Innovation Reform Vision (2008) expresses, Inquiry shifts the focus of education to cognitive abilities such as reasoning with data, constructing an argument and making a logically coherent explanation.

Michael (1990) avers that SAPA (Science, A Process Approach) groups process skills into two types viz basic and integrated. The basic process skills provide the foundation for the integrated skills. Mari (2016) views the act of acquiring knowledge as that which involves the use of process skills like observing, measuring, classifying, experimenting, collection and interpretation of data, making models and operational definition among others. Oloyede (2012) finds that students equipped with science process skills tends to achieve higher than students with low process skills. This is because such students tend to reason intelligently and tackle problem situations more effectively thus leading to higher achievement. POGIL promotes use of activities that promotes self-regulation in learning and could enhance acquisition of science process skills. As Mari (2016) observes, proficiency in use of skills increases when learners are allow to practice such skills and as use of POGIL allow use of skills to solve problems it could enhance acquisition of science skills.

Acquisition of science skills by learners is a manifestation of attainment of formal reasoning. NRC (2016) notes that educational goal is to produce independently thinking and acting individuals. That is

education is meant to groom individuals as formal thinkers. NRC (2016) also specifies the eventual goal of science education which is “to produce individuals capable of understanding and evaluating information that is, or purported to be, scientific in nature and of making decisions that incorporates information appropriately, and more so to produce a sufficient number, of diversified, skilled and motivated future scientists, engineers and other science based individuals”. This type of individual can be regarded as a formal reasoner. This work adapts Piaget’s genetic constructivism, specifically to determine how application of POGIL can bridge the gap of knowledge construction of concrete, through transition to formal reasoning learners in terms of acquisition of science process skills in acid-base concepts.

Constructivism is a theory that is based on the premise that cognition (learning) is the result of mental construction; students learn by fitting new information together with what they already know. Jean Piaget’s cognitivism emphasizes two main functions: organization and adaptation, from these comes Piaget works of intellectual development later coined as genetic constructivism whose reasoning abilities are:

- Pre-operational
- concrete operational
- Transition stage
- Formal stage

Keller, (2017) notes that Piaget enumerates several reasoning types he collectively called ‘formal thought’, this formal reasoning may emerge from concrete reasoning during adolescence, he concludes that whether it does or not, depend in large part on an individual’s experiences. As Keller opines, generally, reasoning that is based on direct experience, concrete objects and familiar activities is classified as concrete reasoning. While reasoning that is based on abstraction and transcending experience is termed as formal thought. In any science classroom at senior secondary school level, it is expected that the learners can be placed on Piaget’s stages of intellectual development as concrete, transition or formal learners expected to have different reasoning abilities.

Fig 1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK ON IMPACT OF POGIL ON ACQUISITION OF SCIENCE SKILLS IN ACIDBASE CONCEPTS AMONG DIFFERENT REASONING ABILITIES

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research employed quasi-experimental control group design which involved the administration of Acquisition of Science Skills in Acid-Base Concepts Instrument (ASSABCI) and Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning (LCTSR). Intact classes were used. Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning (LCTSR), a published instrument was applied to sort both experimental and control groups into concrete, transition and formal reasoners on Piaget level of reasoning. In this study, experimental group was exposed to POGIL for six weeks, while control group was also exposed to lecture method for six weeks.

Acquisition of Science Skills in Acid-Base Concepts Instrument (ASSABCI) was administered as pretest to determine the academic equivalence of both experimental and control groups. The instrument was also administered as post-test to the two groups after POGIL treatment. Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning (LCTSR) was administered to all the sampled students to identify them as concrete, transition and formal reasoners. Hence all sampled students were grouped into four namely: experimental concrete reasoners (ECR); experimental transition reasoners (ETR); control concrete reasoners (CCR) and control transition reasoners (CTR). The researcher intended to include experimental formal reasoners (EFR) and control formal reasoners (CFR) to make six groups but it turned out that with the administration of LCTSR, it becomes clear that none of the sampled students have attained formal thought; the sample could only be sorted out into four groups.

The two intact classes were given teaching intervention of fifty minutes par week for six weeks using the related lesson plans developed for each intact class. The experimental group received treatment (POGIL instruction in acid-base concepts) while the control group were taught traditionally. All the groups were subjected to post-test (to determine the effect of the treatment on students’ science process skill acquisition and to determine the extent to which treatment affect concrete and transition reasoners with respect to science skills). The research design is illustrated below.

Fig 2: Research Design Illustration

Key: S = Sample E = Experimental Group, C = Control Group,
 ECR = Experimental Concrete Reasoners, ETR = Experimental Transition Reasoners;
 CCR = Control Concrete Reasoner,
 CTR = Control Transition Reasoners
 O₁= Acquisition of Science Skills in Acid-Base Concepts Pre-test,
 X₁= POGIL treatment, X₀= no POGIL treatment,
 O₂= Acquisition of Science Skills in Acid-Base Concepts Post-test.

Letter of introduction was collected from the Head of Department which was used to obtain needed data from Educational Resource Centre (ERC). Application was also made to FCT-Secondary Education Board, Education Secretariat to subsequently give further letters of introduction to each of the government secondary schools in Abuja south education zone. The sampled schools (G.S.S Hajj-Camp Gwagwalada and S.F.G. Gwagwalada) and the pilot tested schools (G.D.S.S. Gwagwalada and G.S.S Gwagwalada) the four schools granted their permission and facilitated data gathering processes which include pilot study and administration of pre-test followed by treatment and post-test.

HYPOTHESES

The tested hypotheses are as follows:

1. There is no significant difference in the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy and concrete reasoners taught same concepts using lecture method.
2. The extent, to which the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL, will not be significantly different.

Hypothesis 1 was analyzed using t-test while Hypothesis 2 was analyzed using ANCOVA to establish the homogeneity of the instrument.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Presentations were guided by research questions/hypotheses

Research Question 1: *What is the difference in the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL and concrete reasoners taught same concepts using lecture method?*

In order to answer this question, mean and standard deviation of scores on acquisition of skills among concrete reasoners of experimental and control groups were analyzed and shown in table 1

Table 1 Mean and Standard Deviations of Scores on Acquisition of Skills among Concrete Reasoners of Experimental and Control Groups

Concrete	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Diff
POGIL	27	51.11	11.11	3.03
LECTURE	25	48.08	10.71	

Table 1 shows that the mean score of acquisition of science skills by concrete reasoners in experimental group taught acid-base concepts using POGIL (51.11) is higher than those taught using lecture method (48.08). The mean difference = 3.03, indicating that the mean difference in the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL as against lecture method is 3.03

Research Question 2: *To what extent will the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL be different?*

In answering the question computation of acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners of experimental were made using the descriptive statistics of ANCOVA as shown in table 2.

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviations of acquisition of science skills scores in Experimental Group

POGIL	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Diff
Concrete	27	51.11	1.957	10.553
Transitional	22	61.570	2.169	

As observed in table 2, mean (61.570) of transitional reasoners is higher than the mean (51.017) of concrete reasoners of the experimental group after they were both exposed to POGIL, hence the extent to which the acquisition of science skills of transitional and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL differs with a mean difference of 10.55

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy and concrete reasoners taught same

concepts using lecture method. This hypothesis was tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) shown in table 3

Table 3: Pre-Test and Post-Test Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) Results of Acquisition of Science Skills of Concrete Reasoners taught Acid-Base Concepts using POGIL as against those taught using Lecture Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Decision
Corrected Model	259.303 ^a	2	129.652	1.091	0.344	
Intercept	20335.554	1	20335.554	171.137	0.000	
Pretest	140.041	1	140.041	1.179	0.283	Not Significant
Group	107.424	1	107.424	.904	0.346	
Error	5822.466	49	118.826			
Total	134288.000	52				
Corrected Total	6081.76951					

The result in Table 3 indicates that:

- pretest as main effect has no influence ($p = 0.283$, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance) on the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy and concrete reasoners taught same concepts using lecture method.
- The group as main effect also did not influence their acquisition of science skills ($p = 0.346$, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance).

Therefore, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant differences in the acquisition of science skills between concrete reasoners taught acid base concept using POGIL instructional strategy and concrete reasoners taught same concepts using lecturer method is retained.

H₀₂ The extent to which the acquisition of science skills of transitional and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL will not be significantly different. The hypothesis was tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) shown in table 4.

Table 4 Pre-Test and Post-Test Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) Result of Acquisition of Science Skills of Transitional and Concrete Reasoners in Acid-Base Concepts using POGIL Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Corrected Model	1620.500 ^a	2	810.250	7.839	0.001
Intercept	21004.999	1	21004.999	203.222	.000
Pretest	323.560	1	323.560	3.130	.083
Group	1347.734	1	1347.734	13.039	.001
Error	4754.561	46	103.360		
Total	158698.000	49			
Corrected Total	6375.06148	48			

The result in Table 4 indicates that:

- Pretest as main effect has no influence ($p = 0.083$, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance) on the acquisition of science skills of concrete and transitional reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy.
- The group as main effect influenced their acquisition of science skills after treatment with POGIL strategy ($p = 0.001$, which is less than 0.05 level of significance).

That is the hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL is rejected.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Through the application of Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning, both experimental and control groups were separated into concrete and transitional sub groups according to their reasoning pattern. Two research questions were raised and answered and two research hypotheses were also raised and tested. From the results presented above, the findings are hereunder

- i. There is no significant difference between the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy and concrete reasoners taught same concepts using lecture method.
- ii. The hypothesis which states that “the extent to which the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL is not significantly different” is rejected
- iii. None of the subjects has attained formal reasoning consequently,
- iv. The implication of Piaget’s grouping is that age indicators turn out not to be the streamlining determinant, rather it is now indicating their mental age.
- v. There is a strong correlation between reasoning ability and acquisition of science skills after treatment.

DISCUSSION OF THE MAJOR FINDINGS

The significant difference exists due to the existing difference in their reasoning pattern. Brunner et al, 1956; Sheehan 1970; Schneider & Renner 1980; Huh, 1981) attested to formal reasoners having greater gains in academic performance and acquisition of science process skills when instructed through inquiry based learning involving concrete schemes compare to use of traditional instructional design for formal reasoners.

Likening Brunner’s symbolic stage to Piaget’s concrete; and linking iconic to transitional stage, what is important in teaching the basic concepts according Brunner (1960) is to assist the learners to progressively move from concrete reasoning through transitional to formal reasoning through the utilization of more conceptually adequate schemes of thought such as POGIL.

Huh (1981) explains that positive results with experimental group can be seen as an indication that instructional sequence and material can be effective in enhancing formal thought. The lesson design of POGIL is such instructional sequence and concrete materials. The ability differences of concrete learners which limits them are:

- i. Concrete reasoners view a total system from a limited perspective enabling them to see limited number and types of relationship amongst its parts.
- ii. Concrete reasoners can perform only basic logical operations enabling them to employ hypothetical-deductive reasoning which for the most part is unavailable to the concrete operational thinkers.
- iii. Concrete reasoners make observations and draw inferences from them, but do not consider all possibilities. They respond to difficult problem by applying a related but not necessarily the correct procedures

Analysis shows that there is no significant difference between the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy and concrete reasoners taught same concepts using lecture method. Table 3 shows that pretest as main effect has no influence ($p = 0.283 > 0.05$ level of significance) on the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners in experimental group and concrete reasoners in control group. The group as main effect also did not influence their acquisition of science skills ($p = 0.283 > 0.05$ level of significance). The hypothesis is therefore retained nevertheless; the mean of experimental group is (51.11 > 48.08) is slightly greater than the mean of control group after POGIL treatment. Keller (2017) cited two works, one of which found significant improvement in achievement and the other found no significant improvement in achievement with the use of POGIL in addition to some studies which found no significant improvement in achievement with the use of POGIL. This observation is simply in compliance with two of the implications from scholarly works (Huh 1981; Goodstein & Howe 1978 and Sheehan 1970) which are:

- i. Concrete level students cannot learn concepts which requires advance formal operational thinking irrespective of how the concepts are taught.
- ii. Concrete Inquiry based instruction is more successful if the concepts to be taught are more suitable to the cognitive level of the learners.

The extent to which the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL is not significantly different. The result in Table 4 shows that pretest as main effect has no influence ($p = 0.083 > 0.05$ level of significance) on the acquisition of science skills of concrete and transition reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy. The group as main effect has no significance influence on their acquisition of science skills ($p = 0.001 < 0.05$ level of significance). Rather the instructional strategy applied in teaching the group has significant influence beyond their reasoning pattern. In other words before treatment their differences in acquisition of science skills is not significant but after treatment there is significant difference between the transitional and concrete reasoners. However, it does not mean that there is no gain in acquisition of process skills in the sense that the POGIL treatment led to an appreciable gains in their acquisition of science process skills even though the difference between the transition and concrete groups is significant. This can further be explained by the fact that since the mean of concrete (control) is less than the mean of concrete (experimental) which is also less than the mean of transition (experimental); $(\bar{X} \text{ of concrete (control)} < \bar{X} \text{ of concrete (experimental)} < \bar{X} \text{ of transition (experimental)})$; POGIL is therefore a dependable instructional strategy for fostering science process skills acquisition. Sen, Yalmiz & Geban (2015), arrived at the conclusion that POGIL was superior to the traditionally designed chemistry instruction on students' self regulated learning skills. By implication POGIL improved their potential for reasoning formally through equilibration. It has also demonstrated the use of POGIL in fostering science process skills acquisition. Also, Walker & Warfa (2017) and Pedagogy in Action (n.d) describes POGIL as a pedagogy whose environment represents both classroom and laboratory techniques that builds process skills in the process of content learning through guided inquiry activities, to standard lecture conditions. In collaboration, studies such as Hanib, Suhadi & Indirwati (2017) and Walker (2017) also opine that Process-Oriented Guided-Inquiry Learning (POGIL) is a constructivist approach to science teaching which combined the principles of guided inquiry learning and cooperative learning to foster targeted science skills and enhance conceptual understanding. Pedagogy in Action (n.d) views POGIL as a unique strategy for developing process skills among chemistry students in particular and science students in general. The implication of these is that POGIL is an instructional technology that bridges the acquisition of science process skills between concrete and transitional reasoners. Other implications from scholarly works (Huh 1981; Goodstein & Howe 1978 and Sheehan 1970) are

1. Learning of formal operational concepts can be enhanced for formal operational through use of inquiry learning activities or concrete models during learning process.
2. Concrete inquiry based instruction is superior to formal expository instruction in promoting cognitive developmental for both concrete and formal operational students.
3. Concrete Inquiry based instruction is more successful if the concepts to be taught are more suitable to the cognitive level of the learners.

CONCLUSIONS

The study established the following conclusions:

1. There is no significant difference between the acquisition of science skills of concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL instructional strategy and concrete reasoners taught same concepts using lecture method. Because some of the activities requires formal reasoning, conclusively the scholarly reasons connected to this are:
 - i. Concrete level students cannot learn concepts which requires advance formal operational thinking irrespective of how the concepts are taught.
 - ii. Concrete Inquiry based instruction is more successful if the concepts to be taught are more suitable to the cognitive level of the learners.
2. The hypothesis which states that "the extent to which the acquisition of science skills of transition and concrete reasoners taught acid-base concepts using POGIL is not significantly different" is rejected.

3. POGIL treatment led to an appreciable gain in the acquisition of science process skills of the two groups while the difference in scores between the transition and concrete groups is significant. Conclusively, beside the appreciable gain in acquisition of science skills, POGIL enhances performance of transition and concrete learners and promotes cognitive gains and deep comprehension among transition and concrete learners.
4. A positive strong correlation exists between reasoning ability and acquisition of science process skills.
5. Majority of the students in college-preparatory chemistry classroom are concrete thinkers requiring specific learning cycle approach for effective instruction.

From all the above, it was concluded that science students have the potentials of attaining formal reasoning but science teaching in most secondary schools have not explore these potentials in the students through the adoption of constructive inquiry strategies which are rich in developing metacognitive abilities and constructive thinking among learners in view of developing formal reasoning as a basis for successful teaching and learning of science concepts and related science process skills.

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